

A Dissertation for Term Paper Entitled
**ON GENERATING VARIOUS CANONICAL
FORMS OF LINEAR OPERATORS**

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CERTIFICATE FROM THE SUPERVISOR

This is to certify that the term paper entitled “**ON GENERATING VARIOUS CANONICAL FORMS OF LINEAR OPERATORS**” is submitted by **Debmalya Roy** (UID-21003021041) for the partial fulfillment of M. Sc. Course in Mathematics of Bankura University under my supervision. For the preparation of this term paper some relevant books and papers have been consulted.

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Abstract

A linear operator on a finite dimensional vector space is equivalent to a matrix. So it is quite natural to study a linear operator whose matrix representation is simpler looking. Those representations are called canonical forms of the corresponding linear operator. In our current work we study how to find canonical forms of linear operators on finite dimensional vector spaces. In this process we had to use module theory heavily.

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Introduction

Let V be a finite dimensional vector space over a field F and T be a linear operator on V . If $\dim V = n$, then from basic linear algebra we know that corresponding to an ordered basis there is a matrix of T . Actually there is one-one correspondence between the set of linear operators on an n -dimensional vector space over F and the set of all $n \times n$ matrices over F . So we can use them interchangeably. Now there is no need of discussion that an easy looking matrix is very easy to handle. This motivates us to study those linear operators which have easy looking matrix representations which is generally called canonical representation. In the current work, our goal is to find some of the canonical forms of a linear operator on finite dimensional vector spaces.

In this study, we observe that vector space V over F can be visualized as an $F[x]$ -module. As we take here V as finite dimensional vector space, the module would be a finitely generated $F[x]$ -module. Then to cultivate the module structure of V , here we vividly study module theoretic background until we obtain the fundamental theorem for modules. With the help of that theorem, ultimately, we obtain Jordan canonical forms of a linear operator. This study is not only useful of giving the clarity of the process of finding canonical forms but also helps us to point out some application of module theory in the connection of linear algebra. To prepare this work we have taken help from [1, 2].

Preliminary ideas

In this chapter certain basic definitions and results are presented for their use in the sequel.

We recall the following preliminary notions of module theory from [1, 2].

Definition 1.0.1. Module Let R be a ring. A left R -module is an abelian group $(M, +)$ together with an action of R on M (a map $R \times M \rightarrow M$) denoted by rm for all $r \in R$ and for all $m \in M$ which satisfies the following for all $r, s \in R$, for all $m, n \in M$,

$$(i) \quad (r + s)m = rm + sm$$

$$(ii) \quad (rs)m = r(sm)$$

$$(iii) \quad r(m + n) = rm + rn,$$

$$(iv) \quad 1m = m \text{ (if } R \text{ has multiplicative identity } 1\text{)}.$$

Similarly one can define a right R -module.

Example 1.0.2. (1) If K is a field, then K -vector spaces are K – modules.

(2) The decimal fractions form a module over the integers.

(3) If R is any ring and n is a natural number, then the cartesian product R^n is both a R – module over R if we use the componentwise operations.

Definition 1.0.3. Sub-module Let M be a left R -module. An R -submodule of M is a subgroup $(N, +)$ of $(M, +)$ such that $rn \in N$ for all $r \in R$ and for all $n \in N$.

Example 1.0.4. • Any ring R is a left as well as right R -module.

The submodules of R are precisely the left ideals of R .

• Any abelian group $(G, +)$ is a \mathbb{Z} -module (with the action $(n, a) \mapsto na$).

\mathbb{Z} -submodules of G are precisely the subgroups of $(G, +)$.

• Any vector space V over F is a left as well as right F -module.

The submodules of V are precisely the subspaces of V .

Throughout our discussion, unless mentioned otherwise, an R -module stands for a left R -module.

Definition 1.0.5. In an R -module M , an R -linear combination of elements $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k \in M$ is an element of M having the form

$$r_1 m_1 + \dots + r_k m_k \text{ where the } r_i\text{'s are in } R.$$

Definition 1.0.6. Let A be a subset of an R -module M . Then we call A to be a *spanning set* or *generating set* of M if

$$M = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n a_i + \sum_{j=1}^m r_j x_j \mid m, n \in \mathbb{N}, \text{ each } a_i, x_j \in A, r_j \in R \right\} = \text{Span}A.$$

If R is a ring with 1 then A is said to be a *spanning set* or *generating set* of M if

$$M = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^m r_j x_j \mid m \in \mathbb{N}, \text{ each } x_j \in A, r_j \in R \right\} = \text{Span}A,$$

i.e. each element of M can be expressed as an R -linear combination of finitely many elements of A .

Definition 1.0.7. An R -module M is said to be a *finitely generated R -module* if M has a finite spanning set.

Definition 1.0.8. An R -module M is said to be a *cyclic R -module* if M has a spanning set with cardinality 1.

Definition 1.0.9. In an R -module M , a non-empty subset $S \subseteq M$ is called linearly independent if for any s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n in S and r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n in R , $\sum_{i=1}^n r_i s_i = 0$ implies $r_i = 0$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$ and linearly dependent otherwise.

Definition 1.0.10. A subset B of an R -module M is called a *basis* of M if it is a linearly independent spanning set of M .

A module that has a basis is called a *free module*.

Remark 1.0.11. In a linearly dependent set in an R -module M , an element need not be expressed as an R -linear combination of the other elements which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.12. Consider \mathbb{Z} -module \mathbb{Z} . Then $S := \{2, 3\}$ is linearly dependent as $3 \cdot 2 + (-2) \cdot 3 = 0$. But none of them can be expressed as a \mathbb{Z} -linear combination of the other (as 2 cannot be expressed as an integer multiple of 3 and 3 cannot be written as an integer multiple of 2).

Remark 1.0.13. Minimal Spanning Set need not be a Basis in an R -module M which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.14. Consider \mathbb{Z} -module \mathbb{Z} . Then $S := \{2, 3\}$ is a spanning set here. But S is not linearly independent as $3 \cdot 2 + (-2) \cdot 3 = 0$. Hence S is not a basis here though it is a minimal spanning set since no proper subset of S can span \mathbb{Z} .

Remark 1.0.15. Maximal Linearly Independent Set need not be a Basis in an R -module M which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.16. Consider \mathbb{Z} -module $\mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}_2$. Then $T := \{(1, \bar{0})\}$ is a linearly independent set since $n(1, \bar{0}) = (0, \bar{0})$ for some $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ implies that $n = 0$.

Now let there exists a linearly independent set S which properly contains T . Then consider $x \in S \setminus T$. Then $x = (t, \bar{x})$ where $x = 0$ or 1 and $t \in \mathbb{Z}$. Now $2 \cdot (t, \bar{x}) + (-2t)(1, \bar{0}) = (0, \bar{0})$ proves the maximality of T as a linearly independent set.

But $(1, \bar{1}) \notin \text{Span of } T$ whence T fails to be a basis.

Remark 1.0.17. An R -module M need not have a basis always which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.18. Consider \mathbb{Z} -module \mathbb{Z}_n . Then $na = 0$ for all $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$, i.e. each singleton set $\{a\}$ in \mathbb{Z}_n becomes linearly dependent and hence \mathbb{Z}_n has no basis.

Remark 1.0.19. If an R -module M has a basis, its submodule need not have one, i.e., submodule of a free module need not be free always which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.20. Let $R = \mathbb{Z}[\sqrt{-5}]$ and let P be the ideal generated by $\{2, 1 + \sqrt{-5}\}$, i.e., $P = 2R + (1 + \sqrt{-5})R$. Hence $\{2, 1 + \sqrt{-5}\}$ spans P as an R -module. But $\{2, 1 + \sqrt{-5}\}$ is linearly dependent since

$$(1 + \sqrt{-5}) \cdot 2 + (-2) \cdot (1 + \sqrt{-5}) = 0.$$

Moreover let $x, y \in P$ where at least any of x and y is non-zero.. Then choosing $a = y$ and $b = -x$ we can show that $ax + by = 0$ whence $\{x, y\}$ is a linearly dependent subset of P . Thus a linearly independent subset of P must consist of a single element. But a singleton set cannot span P whence P has no basis.

Remark 1.0.21. An R -module M can have bases with different cardinalities which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.22. Let V be an infinite dimensional vector space over a field K . Let $R = \text{End}(V)$ be the ring of endomorphisms of V . Then for any two positive integers n, m , $R^n \cong R \cong R^m$ as R -modules. Hence for any positive integer n , R -module R has a basis with cardinality n .

Remark 1.0.23. Submodule of a finitely generated R -module M need not be finitely generated always which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.24. Let $R = K[X]$ where K is a field and $X = \{x_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$. Then R -module R is finitely generated by 1. Consider the submodule S of R such that S consists of all the polynomial of R with 0 as constant term. Then S cannot be finitely generated.

Remark 1.0.25. Submodule of a cyclic R -module M need not be cyclic always which is clear from the following example.

Example 1.0.26. Let $R = K[X]$ where K is a field and $X = \{x_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$. Then R -module R is finitely generated by 1 and hence R is a cyclic R -module. Consider the submodule S of R such that S consists of all the polynomial of R with 0 as constant term. Then S cannot be finitely generated and so S is not a cyclic submodule.

Construction of Canonical Forms of linear operator applying Module Theory

In this chapter we study how to deduce canonical forms of a linear operator. To describe this, its connection with modules is also cultivated here.

Definition 2.0.27. Let M be an R -module. We define

$$\text{Tor}(M) := \{m \in M : rm = 0 \text{ for some non-zero } r \in R\}.$$

If R is an integral domain then $\text{Tor}(M)$ becomes a submodule of M .

Definition 2.0.28. An R -module M is said to be a *Torsion Module* if $M = \text{Tor}(M)$.

Definition 2.0.29. Let M be an R -module and N be a submodule of M . Then $(M/N, +)$ with the action $R \times M/N \rightarrow M/N$ defined by $r(m + N) = rm + N$ becomes an R -module which is called quotient module.

Definition 2.0.30. Let N be a submodule of an R -module M . The annihilator of N is $\text{Ann}(N) := \{r \in R : rn = 0 \text{ for all } n \in N\}$.

$\text{Ann}(N)$ always becomes an ideal of R .

2.1 Construction of Rational Canonical Forms of a linear operator

Theorem 2.1.1. (*Fundamental Theorem: Invariant Factor Form*)

Let R be a P.I.D. and let M be a finitely generated R -module.

(1) Then M is isomorphic to the direct sum of finitely many cyclic modules. More precisely,

$$M \cong R^t \oplus R/(a_1) \oplus R/(a_2) \oplus \dots \oplus R/(a_m)$$

for some integer $t \geq 0$ and nonzero elements a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m of R which are not units in R and which satisfy the divisibility relations $a_1 \mid a_2 \mid \dots \mid a_m$

(2) M is torsion free if and only if M is free.

(3) $\text{Tor}(M) \cong R/(a_1) \oplus R/(a_2) \oplus \dots \oplus R/(a_m)$ in the decomposition in (1). In particular M is a torsion module if and only if $t = 0$ and in this case the annihilator of M is the ideal I generated by a_m .

Proof. (i) Let $M = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle$ where $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ is a minimal generating set of M .

Construct R^n which is a free R -module. Let $\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n\}$ be a basis of R -module R^n . Define a map $\phi : R^n \rightarrow M$ by $\phi(b_i) = x_i$ i.e., $\phi(\alpha_1 b_1 + \alpha_2 b_2 + \dots + \alpha_n b_n) = \alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2 + \dots + \alpha_n x_n$.

Now, let $r \in R^n$

$$\text{so, } r = \alpha_1 b_1 + \alpha_2 b_2 + \dots + \alpha_n b_n$$

$$\phi(r) = \alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2 + \dots + \alpha_n x_n$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(r_1 + r_2) &= \phi((\alpha_1 b_1 + \alpha_2 b_2 + \dots + \alpha_n b_n) + (\beta_1 b_1 + \beta_2 b_2 + \dots + \beta_n b_n)) \\ &= \phi((\alpha_1 + \beta_1) b_1 + (\alpha_2 + \beta_2) b_2 + \dots + (\alpha_n + \beta_n) b_n) \\ &= (\alpha_1 + \beta_1) x_1 + (\alpha_2 + \beta_2) x_2 + \dots + (\alpha_n + \beta_n) x_n \\ &= (\alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2 + \dots + \alpha_n x_n) + (\beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n) \\ &= \phi(r_1) + \phi(r_2) \end{aligned}$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \phi(rr_1) &= \phi(r(\alpha_1b_1 + \alpha_2b_2 + \cdots + \alpha_nb_n)) \\
 &= \phi(r\alpha_1b_1 + r\alpha_2b_2 + \cdots + r\alpha_nb_n) \\
 &= r\alpha_1x_1 + r\alpha_2x_2 + \cdots + r\alpha_nx_n \\
 &= r(\alpha_1x_1 + \alpha_2x_2 + \cdots + \alpha_nx_n) \\
 &= r\phi(r_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, ϕ is onto.

Consider $m \in M$.

So, $m = r_1x_1 + r_2x_2 + \cdots + r_nx_n$

Let $r \in R^n = r_1b_1 + r_2b_2 + \cdots + r_nb_n$

Then, $\phi(r) = r_1x_1 + r_2x_2 + \cdots + r_nx_n = m$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ker\phi &= \{r \in R^n \mid \phi(r) = 0\} \\
 &= \{r \in R^n \mid \alpha_1x_1 + \alpha_2x_2 + \cdots + \alpha_nx_n = 0\} \\
 &\neq 0
 \end{aligned}$$

So, ϕ is not one to one.

By 1st **isomorphism theorem**, $R^n / Ker\phi \cong M$.

So, we have a basis $\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$ of R^n and a basis $\{a_1y_1, a_2y_2, \dots, a_my_m\}$ of $Ker\phi$ where a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m are non-zero elements of R such that $a_1 \mid a_2 \mid \cdots \mid a_m$

Now, $R^n = Ry_1 \oplus Ry_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus Ry_n$ [As, $R^n = R \oplus R \oplus \cdots \oplus R$ and $Ry_i \cong R$]

And, $Ker\phi = Ra_1y_1 \oplus Ra_2y_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus Ra_my_m$

So, $M \cong \frac{R^n}{Ker\phi} = \frac{Ry_1 \oplus Ry_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus Ry_n}{Ra_1y_1 \oplus Ra_2y_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus Ra_my_m}$

Define, $\psi : Ry_1 \oplus Ry_2 \oplus \cdots \oplus Ry_n \longrightarrow R/\langle a_1 \rangle \oplus R/\langle a_2 \rangle \oplus \cdots \oplus R/\langle a_m \rangle \oplus R^{n-m}$ such that

$$\psi(\alpha_1y_1, \alpha_2y_2, \dots, \alpha_ny_n) = (\alpha_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle, \alpha_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, \alpha_m + \langle a_m \rangle, \alpha_{m+1}, \alpha_{m+2}, \dots, \alpha_n)$$

Now, $\psi((\alpha_1 + \beta_1)y_1 + (\alpha_2 + \beta_2)y_2 + \cdots + (\alpha_n + \beta_n)y_n)$

$$= (\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle, \alpha_2 + \beta_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, \alpha_m + \beta_m + \langle a_m \rangle, \alpha_{m+1} + \beta_{m+1}, \alpha_{m+2} + \beta_{m+2}, \dots, \alpha_n + \beta_n)$$

$$= (\alpha_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle + \beta_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle, \alpha_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle + \beta_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, \alpha_m + \langle a_m \rangle + \beta_m + \langle a_m \rangle, \alpha_{m+1} + \beta_{m+1}, \dots, \alpha_n + \beta_n)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \beta_{m+1}, \alpha_{m+2} + \beta_{m+2}, \dots, \alpha_n + \beta_n) \\
 & = (\alpha_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle, \alpha_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, \alpha_m + \langle a_m \rangle, \alpha_{m+1}, \alpha_{m+2}, \dots, \alpha_n) + (\beta_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle, \beta_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, \beta_m + \langle a_m \rangle, \beta_{m+1}, \beta_{m+2}, \dots, \beta_n).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Again, } \psi(r_0 r) & = (r_0 \alpha_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle, r_0 \alpha_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, r_0 \alpha_m + \langle a_m \rangle, r_0 \alpha_{m+1}, r_0 \alpha_{m+2}, \dots, r_0 \alpha_n) \\
 & = (r_0(\alpha_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle), (\alpha_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle), \dots, (\alpha_m + \langle a_m \rangle), \alpha_{m+1}, \alpha_{m+2}, \dots, \alpha_n) \\
 & = r_0(\alpha_1 + \langle a_1 \rangle), (\alpha_2 + \langle a_2 \rangle), \dots, (\alpha_m + \langle a_m \rangle), \alpha_{m+1}, \alpha_{m+2}, \dots, \alpha_n)
 \end{aligned}$$

So, ψ is an **R-module morphism**.

ψ is clearly **onto**.

$$\text{Then, } \frac{Ry_1 \oplus Ry_2 \oplus \dots \oplus Ry_n}{Ker\psi} \cong R/\langle a_1 \rangle \oplus R/\langle a_2 \rangle \oplus \dots \oplus R/\langle a_m \rangle \oplus R^{n-m}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ker\psi & = \{(\alpha_1 y_1, \alpha_2 y_2, \dots, \alpha_n y_n) \mid \alpha_k + \langle a_k \rangle = \langle a_k \rangle; k = 1, 2, \dots, m; \text{ and } \alpha_{m+1} = \dots = \alpha_n = 0\} \\
 & = \{(\alpha_1 y_1, \alpha_2 y_2, \dots, \alpha_n y_n) \mid \alpha_k \in \langle a_k \rangle; k = 1, 2, \dots, m; \text{ and } \alpha_{m+1} = \dots = \alpha_n = 0\} \\
 & = \{(\alpha_1 y_1, \alpha_2 y_2, \dots, \alpha_n y_n) \mid \alpha_k \mid a_k; \text{ and } \alpha_{m+1} = \dots = \alpha_n = 0\} \\
 & = \{(r_1 a_1 y_1, r_2 a_2 y_2, \dots, r_m a_m y_m, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \mid r_1, r_2, \dots, r_m \in R\} \\
 & = Ra_1 y_1 \oplus Ra_2 y_2 \oplus \dots \oplus Ra_m y_m.
 \end{aligned}$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned}
 M & \cong \frac{Ry_1 \oplus Ry_2 \oplus \dots \oplus Ry_n}{Ra_1 y_1 \oplus Ra_2 y_2 \oplus \dots \oplus Ra_m y_m} \cong R/\langle a_1 \rangle \oplus R/\langle a_2 \rangle \oplus \dots \oplus R/\langle a_m \rangle \oplus R^{n-m} \\
 M & \cong R/\langle a_1 \rangle \oplus R/\langle a_2 \rangle \oplus \dots \oplus R/\langle a_m \rangle \oplus R^{n-m}
 \end{aligned}$$

If a_i is unit in R then $\langle a_i \rangle = R$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{R}{\langle a_i \rangle} = \{0\}$$

Then we can remove the factor.

So, the a_i 's are non unit.

(ii) M is torsion free.

$$\Leftrightarrow Tor M = \{0\}$$

iff $M \cong R^{n-m}$

$\Leftrightarrow M$ is free.

(iii) In $\frac{R}{\langle a_i \rangle}$

$a_i(r + \langle a_i \rangle) = \langle a_i \rangle = 0_{\frac{R}{\langle a_i \rangle}}$; So, $\frac{R}{\langle a_i \rangle}$ is a torsion module.

$\because R$ is an ID $\Rightarrow a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m \neq 0$

$$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m) \cdot (r + \langle a_1 \rangle, r + \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, r + \langle a_m \rangle)$$

$$= (\langle a_1 \rangle, \langle a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle a_m \rangle) = 0_{R/\langle a_1 \rangle \oplus R/\langle a_2 \rangle \oplus \dots \oplus R/\langle a_m \rangle}$$

So, $R/\langle a_1 \rangle \oplus R/\langle a_2 \rangle \oplus \dots \oplus R/\langle a_m \rangle$ is torsion module.

R^{n-m} is not torsion module as it doesn't have any torsion element.

So, $Tor M \cong R/\langle a_1 \rangle \oplus R/\langle a_2 \rangle \oplus \dots \oplus R/\langle a_m \rangle$. □

Note 2.1.2. The elements $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m \in R$ are called the invariant factors of M and the integer t is called the free rank or the Betty number of M .

• **How will we realize a vector space V over F as an $F[x]$ module?**

Let V be a vector space over the field F and T be a linear operator on V . Then V becomes an $F[x]$ module via T with the following action

$$\begin{aligned} F[x] \times V &\rightarrow V \\ (f(x), v) &\mapsto f(x) \cdot v = (f(T))(v). \end{aligned}$$

• **Construction of canonical forms of linear operators:**

Let V be an n -dimensional vector space over the field F and $T \in L(V, V)$. Clearly, $F[x]$ is a P. I. D. and V is a finitely generated $F[x]$ module ($\because V$ is finite dimensional). Then using **Fundamental Theorem: Invariant Factor Form** we have the following:

$$V \cong \text{Free part of } V \oplus Tor(V).$$

Here V is a torsion $F[x]$ -module, *i.e.*, $V = Tor(V)$ as

$$m(T)(v) = 0 \text{ for all } v \in V$$

where $m(x) \in F[x]$ is the minimal polynomial of T . We also observe that the

$$\text{ann}(V) = \{f(x) \in F[x] : f(T)(v) = 0 \text{ for all } v \in V\} = (m(x))$$

where $(m(x))$ denotes the ideal generated by $m(x)$ in $F[x]$.

Hence in view of **Fundamental Theorem: Invariant Factor Form** we obtain the following:

$$V \cong F[x]/(f_1(x)) \oplus F[x]/(f_2(x)) \oplus \dots \oplus F[x]/(f_m(x))$$

where each of $f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_m(x) \in F[x]$ is monic polynomial with degree at least 1 such that

$$f_1(x) \mid f_2(x) \mid \dots \mid f_m(x).$$

Since V is a torsion module, in view of **Fundamental Theorem: Invariant Factor Form**,

$$\text{Ann}(V) = (f_m(x)) \text{ (Ideal generated by } f_m(x)\text{)}.$$

Hence $f_m(x)$ and $m(x)$ are associates, *i.e.*, $f_m(x)$ is nothing but $m(x)$ up to a unit in $F[x]$. So $f_m(x) = m(x)$ in view of the fact that $f_m(x)$ is monic.

In view of the above decomposition of $F[x]$ -module V we see that vector space V over F can also be decomposed as follows:

$$V \cong F[x]/(f_1(x)) \oplus F[x]/(f_2(x)) \oplus \dots \oplus F[x]/(f_m(x)) \dots (A1)$$

where each of $F[x]/(f_k(x))$, $1 \leq k \leq m$ is a vector space over F .

In view of Equation (A1) we see that following is a basis for the vector space V over F

$$\mathfrak{B} = (\mathfrak{B}_1, \mathfrak{B}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{B}_m)$$

where for each $1 \leq k \leq m$, \mathfrak{B}_k denotes a basis for the vector space $F[x]/(f_k(x))$ over F .

Suppose $f_k(x)$ be the monic polynomial as expressed below:

$$f_k(x) = x^{r_k} + a_{r_k-1}x^{r_k-1} + \dots + a_1x + a_0$$

where $1 \leq k \leq m$. Then by construction of the vector space $F[x]/(f_k(x))$ over F , \mathfrak{B}_k forms a basis of $F[x]/(f_k(x))$ where

$$\mathfrak{B}_k = \{1 + (f_k(x)), x + (f_k(x)), \dots, x^{r_k-1} + (f_k(x))\}.$$

We can express \mathfrak{B}_k in the following way, too:

$$\mathcal{B}_k = \{\bar{1}, \bar{x}, \bar{x}^2, \dots, \bar{x}^{r_k-1}\}$$

where $\bar{x} = x + (f_k(x))$.

Now the matrix of T restricted on $F[x]/(f_k(x))$ with respect to the basis \mathfrak{B}_k can be obtained by operating T on the elements of a basis \mathfrak{B}_k .

Let $v \in \mathfrak{B}_k$. As V is an $F[x]$ -module, so $T(v) = x \cdot v$ (here $f(x) = x$, so $T(v) = f(T)(v) = f(x) \cdot v = x \cdot v$) Now we see how does T operate, *i.e.*, x act on the elements of \mathfrak{B}_k .

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{1} = 1 + (f_k(x)) &\mapsto x + (f_k(x)) = \bar{x} \\
 \bar{x} = x + (f_k(x)) &\mapsto x^2 + (f_k(x)) = \bar{x}^2 \\
 \bar{x}^2 = x^2 + (f_k(x)) &\mapsto x^3 + (f_k(x)) = \bar{x}^3 \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\vdots \\
 \bar{x}^{r_k-2} = x^{r_k-2} + (f_k(x)) &\mapsto x^{r_k-1} + (f_k(x)) = \bar{x}^{r_k-1} \\
 \bar{x}^{r_k-1} = x^{r_k-1} + (f_k(x)) &\mapsto x^{r_k} + (f_k(x)) = \bar{x}^{r_k}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\bar{x}^{r_k} \\
 = &x^{r_k} + (f_k(x)) \\
 = &-a_0 - a_1x - a_2x^2 - \dots - a_{r_k-1}x^{r_k-1} + (f_k(x)) \\
 = &(-a_0 + (f_k(x))) + (-a_1x + (f_k(x))) + (-a_2x^2 + (f_k(x))) - \dots \\
 &+ (-a_{r_k-1}x^{r_k-1} + (f_k(x))) \\
 = &-a_0(1 + (f_k(x))) - a_1(x + (f_k(x))) - a_2(x^2 + (f_k(x))) - \dots \\
 &- a_{r_k-1}(x^{r_k-1} + (f_k(x))) \\
 = &-a_0\bar{1} - a_1\bar{x} - a_2\bar{x}^2 - \dots - a_{r_k-1}\bar{x}^{r_k-1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

So with respect to the above basis \mathfrak{B}_k of $F[x]/(f_k(x))$, the matrix for T restricted on $F[x]/(f_k(x))$ is therefore

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 0 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & -a_0 \\
 1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & -a_1 \\
 0 & 1 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & -a_2 \\
 0 & 0 & \ddots & & & \vdots \\
 \vdots & & \ddots & & & \vdots \\
 0 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 1 & -a_{r_k-1}
 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Definition 2.1.3. Let $a(x) = x^k + a_{k-1}x^{k-1} + \dots + b_1x + b_0$ be any monic polynomial

in $F[x]$. The companion matrix of $a(x)$, denoted by $\mathcal{C}_{a(x)}$ is the following matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & -a_0 \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & -a_1 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & \dots & \dots & -a_2 \\ 0 & 0 & \ddots & & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 1 & -a_{k-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now we observe that each direct summand $F[x]/(f_i(x))$ of V is a T -invariant subspace. So the matrix of T with respect to the basis \mathfrak{B} (where $\mathfrak{B} = (\mathfrak{B}_1, \mathfrak{B}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{B}_m)$ is a basis for V) is the direct sum of the matrix representations of T restricted on $F[x]/(f_i(x))$ with respect to the basis \mathfrak{B}_i , $1 \leq i \leq m$.

Since the matrix representations of T restricted on $F[x]/(f_i(x))$ with respect to the basis \mathfrak{B}_i is the companion matrix $\mathcal{C}_{f_i(x)}$ of $f_i(x)$, the matrix of T with respect to the basis \mathfrak{B} is as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{C}_{f_1(x)} & & & \\ & \mathcal{C}_{f_2(x)} & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & \mathcal{C}_{f_m(x)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

This matrix is called the Rational Canonical form of T .

Remark 2.1.4. Similar operators have same Rational canonical forms.

Observation 2.1.5. It is clear that the characteristic polynomial of the companion matrix of $a(x)$ is $a(x)$. So the characteristic polynomial of the rational canonical form of the operator T is $f_1(x)f_2(x)\dots f_m(x)$, i.e., the product of all of its invariant factors. Also we have already observed that the minimal polynomial of T is the largest invariant factor $f_m(x)$

Example 2.1.6. Let T be a linear operator on \mathbb{R}^6 over \mathbb{R} with the characteristic polynomial $f(x) = (x-2)^2(x-1)^4$ and the minimal polynomial $m(x) = (x-2)(x-1)^2$. Then by the above discussion we can have invariant factor decomposition $f_1(x)|f_2(x)|\dots|f_m(x)$ of T such that $f_1(x)f_2(x)\dots f_m(x) = f(x)$ and $f_m(x) = m(x)$. Then possible invariant factor decompositions of T are:

$$(1) (x-2)(x-1)^2|(x-2)(x-1)^2$$

$$(2) (x - 1)|(x - 2)(x - 1)|(x - 2)(x - 1)^2.$$

Now the companion matrix for $(x - 2)(x - 1)^2 = x^3 - 4x^2 + 5x - 2$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 1 & 0 & -5 \\ 0 & 1 & 4 \end{pmatrix}$$

and the companion matrix for $(x - 2)(x - 1) = x^2 - 3x + 2$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -2 \\ 1 & 3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence the possible Rational canonical forms of T are:

$$\left(\begin{array}{ccc} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 1 & 0 & -5 \\ 0 & 1 & 4 \end{bmatrix} & & 0 \\ & & 0 \\ & & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 1 & 0 & -5 \\ 0 & 1 & 4 \end{bmatrix} \end{array} \right)$$

and

$$\left(\begin{array}{ccc} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \end{bmatrix} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -2 \\ 1 & 3 \end{bmatrix} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 1 & 0 & -5 \\ 0 & 1 & 4 \end{bmatrix} \end{array} \right).$$

Example 2.1.7. Compute Rational Canonical form of matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 & 14 \\ 0 & 3 & -7 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Solution: As it is an upper triangular matrix, its eigenvalues are 2, 2, 3.

so, the characteristic polynomial is $(x - 2)^2(x - 3)$.

Now, $(x - 2)(x - 3) \mid (x - 2)^2(x - 3)$. Now, we've to check whether $(x - 2)(x - 3)$ is minimal or not.

Now , suppose $A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -2 & 14 \\ 0 & 3 & -7 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$

Now, $(A - 2I)(A - 3I) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -2 & 14 \\ 0 & 1 & -7 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 & 14 \\ 0 & 3 & -7 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} = 0_{3 \times 3}$

So, $(x - 2)(x - 3)$ is minimal polynomial.

Now, possible invariant factor decomposition of T is $(x - 2) \mid (x - 2)(x - 3)$.

Hence, the possible rational canonical form of T is $\begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{C}_{x-2} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathcal{C}_{x^2-5x+6} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -6 \\ 0 & 1 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$

Example 2.1.8. Determine all possible rational canonical forms for a linear operator T with characteristic polynomial $x^4(x^2 + 1)^2$ and the minimal polynomial $x^2(x^2 + 1)$.

Solution: Suppose characteristic polynomial $C_A(x) = x^4(x^2 + 1)^2$.

So, we should have invariant factor decompositions $f_1(x) \mid f_2(x) \mid \dots \mid f_m(x)$ of T such that $f_1(x)f_2(x)\dots f_m(x) = C_A(x)$ and $f_m(x) = x^2(x^2 + 1)$ (minimal polynomial).

So, possible invariant factor decompositions of T are:

1. $x^2(x^2 + 1) \mid x^2(x^2 + 1)$
2. $x \mid x(x^2 + 1) \mid x^2(x^2 + 1)$

Now, the companion matrix for $x^2(x^2 + 1) = x^4 + x^2$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The companion matrix for $x(x^2 + 1)$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

If each A_i and A_j ($i \neq j$) are comaximal, then the above map is surjective and

$$A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_k = A_1 A_2 \dots A_k$$

and hence

$$R/(A_1 A_2 \dots A_k) = R/(A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_k) \cong R/A_1 \times R/A_2 \times \dots \times R/A_k.$$

Let R be a PID and $a (\neq 0) \in R$. Since R is a UFD, $a = up_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ where the p_i 's are distinct primes in R and u is a unit. Now for each $i \neq j$,

$$(p_i^{\alpha_i}) + (p_j^{\alpha_j}) = R$$

as the sum of these two ideals is generated by $\gcd(p_i, p_j) = 1$. Hence $(p_i^{\alpha_i})$ and $(p_j^{\alpha_j})$ are comaximal.

Then

$$(p_1^{\alpha_1})(p_2^{\alpha_2}) \dots (p_s^{\alpha_s}) = (p_1^{\alpha_1}) \cap (p_2^{\alpha_2}) \cap \dots \cap (p_s^{\alpha_s}) = (a)$$

as

$$\text{lcm}((p_1^{\alpha_1}), (p_2^{\alpha_2}), \dots, (p_s^{\alpha_s})) = a$$

. Then by CRT,

$$R/(a) \cong R/(p_1^{\alpha_1}) \oplus R/(p_2^{\alpha_2}) \oplus \dots \oplus R/(p_s^{\alpha_s})$$

as rings and also as R -modules.

Now if we apply the above discussion to our **Fundamental Theorem: Invariant Factor Form**, we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 2.2.2. *Fundamental theorem: Elementary divisor form*

Let R be a PID and M be a finitely generated R -module. Then M is the direct sum of a finite number of cyclic modules whose annihilators are either (0) or generated by powers of primes in R , i.e.,

$$M \cong R^r \oplus R/(p_1^{\alpha_1}) \oplus R/(p_2^{\alpha_2}) \oplus \dots \oplus R/(p_s^{\alpha_s})$$

where $r \geq 0$ is an integer and $p_1^{\alpha_1}, \dots, p_s^{\alpha_s}$ are positive powers of primes (not necessarily distinct) in R .

Those prime powers $p_1^{\alpha_1}, \dots, p_s^{\alpha_s}$ are called elementary divisors of M .

Let V be a finite dimensional vector space over a field F and T be a linear operator on V . Then V is an $F[x]$ -module and we obtain the rational canonical form of T .

Suppose the invariant factors $f_1(x), \dots, f_m(x)$ of T in its rational canonical form can be factorized linearly (we can consider F be algebraically closed). Then by the **Fundamental Theorem: Elementary divisors Form**, we obtain

$$V \cong F[x]/((x - \lambda_1)^{k_1}) \oplus F[x]/((x - \lambda_2)^{k_2}) \oplus \dots \oplus F[x]/((x - \lambda_t)^{k_t}).$$

Since for any eigen value λ ,

$$\{1 + ((x - \lambda)^k), x + ((x - \lambda)^k), \dots, x^{k-1} + ((x - \lambda)^k)\},$$

i.e.,

$$\{\bar{1}, \bar{x}, \dots, \bar{x}^{k-1}\}$$

is a basis of $F[x]/((x - \lambda)^k)$,

$$\mathfrak{B}_\lambda = \{\bar{1}, \bar{x} - \lambda, (\bar{x} - \lambda)^2, \dots, (\bar{x} - \lambda)^{k-1}\}$$

is also a basis of $F[x]/((x - \lambda)^k)$.

Now we see how does T operate, i.e., x act on the elements of \mathfrak{B}_λ (observing that $x = \lambda + (x - \lambda)$ and $(\bar{x} - \lambda)^k = 0$).

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{1} &\mapsto \lambda \bar{1} + (\bar{x} - \lambda) \\ (\bar{x} - \lambda) &\mapsto \lambda (\bar{x} - \lambda) + (\bar{x} - \lambda)^2 \\ &\vdots \\ &\vdots \\ &\vdots \\ &\vdots \\ (\bar{x} - \lambda)^{k-2} &\mapsto \lambda (\bar{x} - \lambda)^{k-2} + (\bar{x} - \lambda)^{k-1} \\ (\bar{x} - \lambda)^{k-1} &\mapsto \lambda (\bar{x} - \lambda)^{k-1} + (\bar{x} - \lambda)^k \\ &= \lambda (\bar{x} - \lambda)^{k-1}. \end{aligned}$$

So with respect to the above basis \mathfrak{B}_λ , the matrix representation for the operator T restricted to the T -invariant subspace $F[x]/((x - \lambda)^k)$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \lambda & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & \lambda & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \ddots & & & 0 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & \lambda \end{pmatrix}.$$

Definition 2.2.3. Jordan block

The $k \times k$ matrix with λ along the main diagonal and 1 along the first sub-diagonal depicted above is called $k \times k$ **elementary Jordan matrix with eigenvalue** λ or **the Jordan block of size k with eigenvalue** λ .

Applying the above process to each of the cyclic factors of V in its elementary divisor decomposition we obtain a matrix of T as the direct sum of the Jordan blocks corresponding to the elementary divisors of V .

So we obtain here a matrix of T which is block diagonal with Jordan blocks along the diagonal, i.e.,

$$\begin{pmatrix} J_1 & & & \\ & J_2 & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & J_t \end{pmatrix}.$$

This matrix is called Jordan canonical form for T .

Observation 2.2.4. • (1) If a matrix A is similar to a diagonal matrix D , then D is the Jordan canonical form of A .

• (2) Two matrices are similar if and only if they have same Jordan canonical form.

Example 2.2.5. Let T be a linear operator on \mathbb{R}^6 over \mathbb{R} with the characteristic polynomial $f(x) = (x - 2)^2(x - 1)^4$ and the minimal polynomial $m(x) = (x - 2)(x - 1)^2$.

We already know that we can have invariant factor decomposition $f_1(x)|f_2(x)|\dots|f_m(x)$ of T such that $f_1(x)f_2(x)\dots f_m(x) = f(x)$ and $f_m(x) = m(x)$. Then possible invariant factor decompositions of T are:

$$(1) (x - 2)(x - 1)^2|(x - 2)(x - 1)^2$$

$$(2) (x - 1)|(x - 2)(x - 1)|(x - 2)(x - 1)^2.$$

Then the corresponding elementary divisors are:

$$(1) (x - 2), (x - 1)^2, (x - 2), (x - 1)^2 \text{ and}$$

$$(2) (x - 1), (x - 2), (x - 1), (x - 2)(x - 1)^2.$$

Corresponding the above elementary divisors all the Jordan blocks are 1×1 except of $(x - 1)^2$. Now the Jordan block for $(x - 1)^2$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence the possible Jordan canonical forms of T are:

$$\left(\begin{array}{cccc} [2] & \cdot & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & [2] & \cdot \\ 0 & \cdot & \cdot & \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{array} \right) \text{ and}$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{cccc} [1] & \cdot & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & [2] & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & [1] & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & [2] & \cdot \\ 0 & \cdot & \cdot & \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{array} \right).$$

Bibliography

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